

Studies on Photoreaction of *endo*-Tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undecadienones in Excited Singlet State[†]

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Manuscript received 31 July 1998

Photochemical reaction of *endo*-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undecadienones 1-5 and 8, 9 upon singlet excitation has been investigated. A novel photodecarbonylation has been observed.

Photochemical reactions of β,γ -enones have stimulated a great deal of interest¹⁻³ which is further enhanced due to their synthetic potential^{2,3}. Though β,γ -enones may undergo a variety of photoreactions characteristic of alkene and carbonyl chromophore, 1,3-acyl shift and 1,2-acyl shift (oxadi- π methane rearrangement) are the two unique molecular rearrangements observed upon singlet (¹S) and triplet (³T) excitation of rigid β,γ -enones^{1,4}.

We recently described² one aspect of the photoreaction of β,γ -enones namely, the [1,2]-acyl shift in various *endo*-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undecane systems having α -methoxy- β,γ -enone group upon triplet (³T) excitation and demonstrated its synthetic potential for efficient and rapid creation of linearly fused *cis:anti:cis* triquinanes in a stereospecific fashion. In continuation with our studies on photoreactions of complex β,γ -enones, we thought to explore photoreaction of β,γ -enones, upon singlet (¹S) excitation. In this context we investigated the photochemical behaviour of *endo*-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undecadienones 1-5 and 8, 9 having α -methoxy- β,γ -enone and α -hydroxy- β,γ -enone chromophore respectively, upon direct excitation³. We wish to describe herein a novel photodecarbonylation during direct excitation of the aforementioned β,γ -enones.

1. R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃2. R₁ = R₂ = CH₃3. R₁ = CH₂CH=CH₂,
R₂ = CH₃4. R₁ = R₂ = H

5

8. R₁ = R₃ = CH₃, R₂ = H9. R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = CH₃

cyclopentadiene, following a procedure developed in our laboratory^{2c,5} (Scheme 1). The structures and stereochemistry of the adducts were thoroughly established through their high field ¹H, ¹³C nmr and other spectral data.

Scheme 1

Towards our studies on the photochemical reaction of the aforementioned chromophoric systems in excited singlet (¹S) state, first a solution of **2** in benzene was irradiated with Hg vapour lamp (400 W, APP) for 2.5 h in a pyrex immersion well (Scheme 2). Removal of the solvent followed by careful chromatography of the photolysate furnished a less polar product in good yield (54%) to which structure **12** was assigned on the basis of its spectral data.

Scheme 2

The ir spectrum of **12** did not show any absorption band due to carbonyl group, the presence of a cyclopropane ring was clearly evident from its ¹H nmr (300 MHz) spectrum which showed signals at δ 1.1 (1H, dd, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 6 Hz) and 0.64 (1H, d, J 9 Hz) for the protons at the cyclopropane ring junctions⁶. Other characteristic resonances were observed at δ 5.74 (1H, m), and 4.71 (1H, d with fine str, J 6 Hz) for olefinic protons in the five-membered ring and vinyl ether moiety respectively. The signal for methoxy group was shown at δ 3.50 (3H, s), and the two methyls on the

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of chromophoric systems 1-5 has already been described^{2c}. The *endo*-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undecadienones 8 and 9 were prepared in a single step from the corresponding phenols 6 and 7 via *in situ* generation of 6-hydroxycyclohexa-2,4-dienones and their interception with

[†] Dedicated with respect to Dr. Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

cyclopropane ring were observed at δ 1.07 and 0.85 as singlets. In addition, it exhibited signals at δ 3.24 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz, doubly allylic ring junction H) and 2.88 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz, ring junction H), 2.72 (1H, m, ring junction H), 2.68 (1H, ddd, J_1 12 Hz, J_2 6 Hz, J_3 ~3 Hz, allylic methylene), 2.3 (1H, m of dd, J_1 12 Hz, allylic methylene). ¹³C nmr spectrum of **12** also showed signals at δ 155.91 (s), 90.48 (d), 132.05 (d) and 129.54 (d) for the olefinic carbons of vinyl ether moiety and cyclopentene ring. Resonances at δ 54.00 (q), 41.89 (t), 28.11 (q) and 15.03 (q) corresponding to carbon atoms of methoxy group, allylic methylene and methyl groups⁷ were also observed in addition to other signals. It is indeed surprising to note that the usual [1,3]-acyl shift product of type **10** was not obtained in the above photoreaction. In order to check the generality and scope of the photoreaction, we also explored the photochemical reaction of other tricyclic systems **1**, **3-5** under the above experimental conditions. Irradiation of all the chromophoric systems **1** and **3-5** were found to give the corresponding decarbonylated products **11**, **13-15**, respectively (Scheme 3). The structures of all the products were clearly revealed from their spectral data. It is remarkable to note that the direct irradiation of the dien-dione **5** containing an additional, highly reactive α,β -enone chromophore, also yielded the decarbonylated product **15** whose structure was deduced from the following spectral data. The ir spectrum of **15** showed absorption bands at 1705, 1670 cm^{-1} . Its ¹H nmr (300 MHz) spectrum exhibited characteristic signals at δ 7.57 (1H, dd, J_1 6 Hz, J_2 3 Hz), 6.16 (1H, dd, J_1 6 Hz, J_2 ~3 Hz) and 4.77 (1H, dd, J_1 5 Hz, J_2 ~2 Hz) corresponding to β -proton of α,β -enone, α -proton of α,β -enone and olefinic proton of vinyl ether moiety respectively. It further showed signals at δ 3.58 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.24 (1H, br d with str, J 8 Hz) and 2.72 (1H, d, J 8 Hz) for methoxy

proton, proton at the doubly allylic ring junction and the proton at the ring junction α to carbonyl group. Furthermore, signals were observed at δ 1.14 (total 5H, multiplets merged with a singlet) and 0.9 (3H, s) for methyl group and the protons at cyclopropane ring junctions⁶. The structure **15** for the above photoproduct was also supported from its ¹³C nmr spectrum which displayed signals at δ 211.21, for enone carbonyl present in the five-membered ring⁷ and 164.58, 152.13, 131.80, 91.92 for four olefinic carbons present in its molecular structure. In addition, signals were observed at δ 54.26, 44.10, 42.94, 27.22, 22.57, 21.99, 20.84, and 15.04 for other methine, methyl and quaternary carbons. Mass spectrum of the compound showed a peak at m/z 204 corresponding to its molecular ion.

It is also interesting to note that the chromophoric system **4** which is devoid of substituents at the carbon α' to the carbonyl group of the β,γ -enone groups, also furnished the decarbonylated product **14**. Though the volatility of **14** hampered its isolation and determination of yield, it was easily characterized through its ¹H nmr (300 MHz) spectrum.

As we have mentioned earlier, it was surprising that no product from the usual [1,3]-acyl shift reaction was obtained during the above photoreaction. Such type of photodecarbonylation is generally not observed during singlet excitation of β,γ -enones^{1,4}, though other reactions such as ketene formation and fragmentations are known^{8,9}. The detailed mechanism of formation of the decarbonylated products during the above photoreaction is difficult to suggest at this moment. Apparently it proceeds through initial α -cleavage leading to the biradicals **16a** and **16b**, and the latter cyclizes to give the [1,3]-acyl shift product of type **17** which on subsequent decarbonylation gives the final product **18** (Scheme 4). This contention is based on the preliminary observation that [1,3]-acyl shift product is formed (tlc, ir) during initial stages of the photoreaction which disappears after continued irradiation and the formation of the final product is observed^{3,10}. In this context it may be noted that cyclobutanones are known to undergo photodecarbonylation upon excitation¹¹. However, the possibility of decarbonylation after initial α -cleavage can not be ruled out.

In order to study the effect of substitution on this photodecarbonylation reaction, we also investigated the photoreaction of various other annulated-bicyclo[2.2.2]-undecadienones having hydroxyl groups at the α' -carbon in addition to β,γ -enone group, upon direct excitation. Interestingly, the irradiation of 1,8-dimethyl-8-hydroxytricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]undeca-3,10-dien-9-one **8**, under similar conditions led to the formation of an inseparable mixture of 2-acetyl-5-methylbicyclo[4.3.0^{1,6}]nona-3,7-diene **19a** and 2-acetyl-5-methylbicyclo[4.3.0^{1,6}]nona-4,7-diene **19b**, in the ratio of 11 : 1. The ¹H nmr spectrum (300 MHz) of the

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

photoproduct **19** showed characteristic signals at δ 2.15 (s) and 1.05 (d, $J \sim 7.5$ Hz) corresponding to the major isomer **19a**. While weak signals were observed at δ 1.88 (br s) and 1.15 (d, $J \sim 7.5$ Hz) corresponding to olefinic methyl and methyl group on the allylic carbon of the minor isomer **19b**. In addition, other signals were observed at δ 5.89–5.70 (m), 3.1–2.97 (complex m), 2.56 (dd with str, $J_1 \sim 16.5$ Hz, J_2 10.5 Hz), 2.29 (m), 2.04 (d with str, J 16.5 Hz) for other methine and methylene protons for both the isomers. The ^{13}C nmr spectrum also showed characteristic resonances for the isomer **19a** at δ 207.76 (CO), 137.61, 131.81, 130.65 and 124.03 for the sp^2 carbons and at δ 54.80, 49.13, 40.83, 36.33, 30.03, 28.15 for other methine and methylene carbons. Further support to the structure was provided by the mass spectrum which showed a peak at m/z 176 for its molecular ion. Similarly, the irradiation of **9** also yielded the corresponding photodecarbonylated products **20a** and **20b** as a mixture containing one of the isomers in major amounts (^1H nmr, 300 MHz). However, it was difficult to find out the ratio of the two isomers.

Scheme 5

The formation of the photoproducts **19** and **18** during the irradiation of **8** and **9** can be rationalized as shown in Scheme 6. Initial α -acyl cleavage followed by decarbonylation apparently led to the formation of diradical **22** which is converted to **23** via loss of a hydrogen radical from OH group. Subsequent capture of hydrogen radical at either of

the allylic centers gives the products (Scheme 6). However, further work is required to support the proposed mechanism.

Scheme 6

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 681 and Nicolet Impact-400 FT IR spectrophotometer, uv spectra on a Schmadzu 260 instrument, and ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Varian VXR 300 instrument, all the samples being dilute solutions in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis was done on a CEST 1106 instrument. All the organic extracts were dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate.

8-Hydroxy-1,8-dimethyl-endo-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]-undeca-3,10-diene-9-one (8): To a mixture of 2,6-dimethylphenol **6** (2.0 g, 17.8 mmol), cyclopentadiene (5 ml, excess) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB; 0.150 g, 0.4 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 ml), was added an aqueous solution of sodium metaperiodate (8 g, 37.4 mmol) dropwise with stirring at 5° . After stirring for 8 h, the dichloromethane layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (4×50 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with water (2×20 ml), brine (2×20 ml) and dried. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue chromatographed on silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) gave the adduct **8** (2.9 g, 80%), m.p. 85° (Found : C, 76.97, H, 8.07. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 76.47; H, 7.84); λ_{max} (MeOH) 306 (w), 212 (s) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3440, 1710 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.29 (1H, dd, J_1 8 Hz, J_2 7 Hz, γ -H of β,γ -enone group), 5.77–5.70 (2H, m, olefinic H), 5.56–5.51 (1H, m, olefinic H), 3.29–3.19 (1H, m, methine H), 2.95 (1H, complex m of d, J 6 Hz, methine H),

2.85 (1H, complex m of d, J 9 Hz, methine H), 2.55 (1H, dd with str, J_1 17 Hz, J_2 10 Hz, methylene of cyclopentene ring), 2.42 (1H, s, OH), 2.00 (1H, complex m of d, J 17 Hz, methylene H), 1.26 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 215.18 (s, CO), 134.07 (d), 133.03 (two carbons), 128.12 (d) (olefinic carbons), 72.64 (s), 55.90 (d), 51.65 (s), 48.10 (d), 38.48 (t, CH_2), 34.50 (d), 25.99 (q, CH_3), 15.25 (q, CH_3); m/z 204 (M^+).

8-Hydroxy-1,8,10-trimethyl-endo-tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{2,6}]-undec-3,10-dien-9-one (9) : To a solution of 2,4,6-trimethylphenol 7 (2.0 g, 15.8 mmol), cyclopentadiene (5 ml) and cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB; 0.15 g, 0.4 mmol) in dichloromethane, was added an aqueous solution of sodium metaperiodate (8 g, 37.4 mmol) dropwise with stirring at 5°. After stirring for 8 h, the dichloromethane layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with dichloromethane (4×50 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with water (2×20 ml), brine (2×20 ml) and dried. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed on silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) gave the adduct 9 (3.0 g, 87%), m.p. 109° (Found : C, 77.07; H, 8.63. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 77.06; H, 8.25%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 308 (w), 223 (s) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3440, 1720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.74 (1H, d with long range coupling, J 6 Hz, β -H of β,γ -enone group), 5.48 (1H, d with str, J_1 6 Hz, olefinic H), 5.26 (1H, m, olefinic H), 3.24–3.14 (1H, m, methine H), 2.82 (1H, m of d, J 9 Hz, methine H), 2.69 (1H, dd, $J_1 = J_2 = 2$ Hz), 2.55 (1H, m of dd, J_1 17 Hz, J_2 9 Hz, methylene H of cyclopentene ring), 2.30 (1H, br, OH), 1.94 (1H, m of d, methylene H, overlapped with another signal), 1.88 (3H, d, J 2 Hz, olefinic CH_3), 1.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.21 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 215 (s, CO), 142 (s), 134 (d), 128 (d), 124 (d) (olefinic carbons), 72 (s), 55 (d), 54 (d), 51 (s), 38 (t, CH_2), 34 (d), 24 (q, CH_3), 23 (q, CH_3), 15 (q, CH_3); m/z 218 (M^+).

2-Methoxy-5-methyltricyclo[5.3.0.0^{4,6}]deca-2,9-diene (11) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone 1 (0.2 g, 0.98 mmol) in benzene under a atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of the solvent and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) of the crude product gave 11 (0.08 g, 54%); ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.79–5.69 (2H, m, olefinic H), 4.63 (d with structure, J ~5 Hz, olefinic H), 3.51 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.83 (1H, m), 2.70–2.62 (2H, m), 2.37–2.30 (1H, m), 1.40 (1H, m, cyclopropane H), 0.96–0.85 (total 5H, multiplets merged with a singlet, CH_3 and cyclopropane ring junction H); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.09 (=C–OMe), 132.07, 129.67 (olefinic carbon), 89.11 (HC=C–OMe), 54.01 (OCH_3), 46.96 (CH), 41.56 (CH_2), 33.81 (CH), 17.44, 17.16, 13.67 (cyclopropane C), 7.79 (CH_3) (major isomer).

2-Methoxy-5,5-dimethyltricyclo[5.3.0.0^{4,6}]deca-2,9-diene (12) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone 2 (0.2 g, 0.91 mmol) in benzene under nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of solvent and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) of the crude residue furnished 12 (0.09 g, 54%); ν_{max} (neat) 3050, 3000, 2950, 1650 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.74 (1H, m, olefinic H), 5.68 (1H, m, olefinic H), 4.71 (1H, d, with fine structure, J 6 Hz, olefinic H of vinyl ether), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.88 (1H, br d, J 8 Hz, methine H), 2.72 (1H, m, ring junction H), 2.68 (1H, m of ddd, J_1 12 Hz, J_2 6 Hz, J_3 ~3 Hz, allylic methylene), 2.3 (1H, m of dd, J 12 Hz, allylic methylene), 1.12 (1H, dd, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 6 Hz, cyclopropane ring junction H), 1.07 (3H, s, CH_3), 0.85 (3H, s, CH_3), 0.64 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, cyclopropane ring junction H); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.91 (s), 132.05 (d), 129.54 (d), 90.48 (d) (olefinic carbons), 54.00 (q, OCH_3), 46.69, 41.89 (t, allylic CH_2), 34.23, 28.11 (q, CH_3), 26.19, 22.92, 22.54, 15.03 (q, CH_3); m/z 190 (M^+).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-5-allyltricyclo[5.3.3.0^{4,6}]deca-2,9-diene (13) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone 3 (0.15 g, 0.61 mmol) in benzene under a atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of the solvent and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) of the residue gave 13 (0.046 g, 35%); ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.90–5.69 (3H, m, olefinic H), 5.03 (1H, d with str, J 5 Hz, olefinic H), 4.99 (1H, br s with str, olefinic H), 4.70 (1H, d with str, J 5 Hz, HC=C–OMe), 3.52 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.87 (1H, br d, J ~9 Hz, ring junction methine H), 2.76–2.64 (2H, m), 2.32 (1H, m), 1.98 (2H, br d, J ~7 Hz, allylic methylene H of the side-chain), 1.20 (1H, dd, J_1 ~9 Hz, J_2 5 Hz, cyclopropane ring junction H), 0.87 (3H, s, CH_3), 0.72 (d, J ~9 Hz, cyclopropane H); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.14 (C–OMe), 136.72, 131.96, 129.50 (=CH), 115.58 (CH_2), 90.15 (HC=C–OMe), 53.97 (OCH_3), 46.66 (CH), 46.18 (CH_2), 41.73 (CH_2), 34.17 (CH), 26.45 (quaternary C of cyclopropane ring), 24.84, 21.21 (cyclopropane C), 12.38 (CH_3). Assignments were made with the help of spectrum recorded in DEPT mode.

2-Methoxytricyclo[5.3.0.0^{4,6}]deca-2,9-dien-8-one (14) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone 4 (0.2 g, 1.05 mmol) in benzene under a atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of the solvent and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) of the residue gave 14 (calculation of yield was difficult due to high volatility of the product); ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.84 (1H, m, olefinic H), 5.75 (1H, m, olefinic H), 4.86 (1H, d, with str, J ~6 Hz, HC=C–OMe), 3.45 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.94 (2H, m), 2.55 (1H, m), 2.31 (1H, m), 1.28 (1H, m, cyclopropane H), 1.10 (1H, m, cyclopropane H), 0.84 (1H, m, cyclopropane H), 0.38 (1H, m, cyclopropane H).

2-Methoxy-5,5-dimethyltricyclo[5.3.0.0^{4,6}]deca-2,9-dien-8-one (15) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone **5** (0.15 g, 0.64 mmol) in benzene under a atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of the solvent and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) of the residue gave **15** (0.046 g, 35%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1705, 1670 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.57 (1H, dd, J_1 6 Hz, J_2 3 Hz, β -H of α,β -enone group), 6.16 (1H, dd, J_1 6 Hz, J_2 ~3 Hz, α -H of α,β -enone moiety), 4.77 (1H, dd, J_1 5 Hz, J_2 ~2 Hz, HC-COMe), 3.58 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.24 (br d, J ~8 Hz, allylic ring junction H), 2.72 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H α to CO), 1.25–1.14 (total 5H, multiplets overlapped with a singlet, CH_3 and cyclopropane H), 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 211.21 (CO), 164.58, 152.13 (HC=COMe), 131.80 (olefinic C), 91.92 (HC=COMe), 54.26 (OCH_3), 44.10, 42.94, 27.22, 22.57, 21.99, 20.84, 15.04; m/z 204 (M^+). Assignments were made in APT mode.

5-Acetyl-2-methylbicyclo[4.3.0]nona-3,8-diene (19) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone **8** (0.2 g, 0.98 mmol) in benzene under a atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) gave a mixture of **19a** and **19b** (0.12 g, 66%) : major isomer **19a**; ν_{\max} (neat) 1720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.89–5.70 (4H, m, olefinic H), 3.1–2.97 (3H, complex m), 2.56 (1H, dd with str, J_1 ~16.5 Hz, J_2 10.5 Hz, methylene H of cyclopentene ring), 2.29 (1H, m), 2.15 (3H, s, acetyl CH_3), 2.04 (3H, d with str, J 16.5 Hz, CH_3), 1.05 (3H, d, J ~7.5 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 207.76 (CO), 137.61, 131.81, 130.65, 124.03 (olefinic carbons), 54.80 (d), 49.13 (d), 40.83 (t), 36.33 (d), 30.03 (d), 28.15 (q), 18.34 (q); m/z 176 (M^+).

5-Acetyl-2,4-dimethylbicyclo[4.3.0]nona-3,8-diene (20) : Irradiation of a solution of the ketone **9** (0.2 g, 0.91 mmol) in benzene under an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 h, followed by removal of the solvent under reduced pressure and column chromatography (petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, 98 : 2) furnished a mixture of **20a**, **b** (0.1 g, 60%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1700 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.64 (2H, m, olefinic H), 5.41 (1H, br d, J 2.5 Hz, olefinic H), 3.17–3.02 (2H, multiplets), 2.89 (1H, br d, J 2 Hz), 2.51 (1H, dd with str, J_1 16 Hz, J_2 9 Hz, methylene H), 2.19–2.04 (total 4H, m, singlet of CH_3 overlapped with multiplets), 1.96–1.91 (1H, m), 1.88 (3H, dd, J_1 ~2 Hz, J_2 ~1.5 Hz, CH_3 -CH), 1.02 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3 -CH); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz,

CDCl_3) δ 207.10 (CO), 132.21, 131.99, 131.57, 130.88, 60.08 (d), 49.00 (d), 40.22 (t), 36.95 (d), 30.78 (d), 27.79 (q), 24.87 (q), 18.34 (q).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.T.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Fellowship and the other (V.S.) is thankful to D.S.T., New Delhi, for financial support. The authors are grateful to R.S.I.C. for providing spectral facilities.

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